
172. The basic angle

IN THE LANGUAGE of space astrometry, and specifically for ESA's space astrometry missions Hipparcos and Gaia, the 'basic angle' is the angle between the instrument's two viewing directions on the sky. For Hipparcos, the basic angle was 58° . For Gaia it is $106^\circ 5'$.

What is the reason for the two fields of view in the first place? How is the angle between them chosen? And why is it so different for Hipparcos and Gaia?

TO START at the beginning: the main reason for making astrometric measurements from space is to avoid the phase fluctuations caused by Earth's turbulent atmosphere. The effect is particularly important in the lowest 10 km or so, the troposphere, and is driven by convective heating rising from the Earth's surface. The turbulence affects light rays passing through the atmosphere, and causes the familiar twinkling of star light.

The thinner atmospheres of high mountain sites diminishes but cannot eliminate these turbulence-driven effects. Over the past 20–30 years, a combination of adaptive optics, interferometers and laser 'guide stars' has succeeded in combatting atmospheric effects over small angles of up to a few degrees, but the atmosphere still imposes an impenetrable barrier over the large angles needed for an all-sky celestial reference frame.

THERE ARE MANY technical challenges in reaching the positional accuracies that are targeted today. The 1 milli-arcsec of Hipparcos corresponds to the angular size of a golf ball viewed from across the Atlantic. The Gaia accuracies of 10 micro-arcsec correspond to the 'Bohr' radius of a hydrogen atom at a distance of 1 m.

Space offers three other big advantages in achieving these demanding accuracies. The 'weightless' environment eliminates effects introduced by the flexing of telescopes under their own weight as the supporting structures are steered to observe different parts of the sky.

And the stable thermal environment helps to minimise the tiny thermo-mechanical distortions as ground-based observatories go through their inevitable day and night cycles of warming and cooling.

A THIRD major complication is that any telescope on Earth can observe only part of the sky at any one time: a telescope in the northern hemisphere only ever sees the northern skies. Even so, it still requires a year to elapse for the entire region to be observable at night. A grid of star positions spanning the entire sky can only be constructed from a vast spider web of thousands of geometrical triangulations from separate telescopes observing accessible portions of the sky at different times.

Like medieval surveys of the Earth made with early instruments, the result of centuries of celestial cartography pre-Hipparcos was a map of the sky, but one which was greatly warped and distorted.

Positions were quite unreliable much below a second of arc, and plagued by unknown errors. Within this distorted reference system, the determination of stellar parallaxes and proper motions at the angular accuracies demanded was simply impossible.

A SINGLE TELESCOPE operating above the atmosphere still cannot create a global reference system free of medium- and large-scale distortions. Imagine trying to create a map of the Earth with a 1-m ruler: local measurements might be tied together well, but the distance from Paris to Warsaw would be hopelessly inaccurate.

The solution, first proposed by French astronomer Pierre Lacroute in the 1960s, is a telescope with *two* widely separated fields of view, superimposed at the same focal plane. As I will outline below, being able to measure accurate relative star positions over wide separations on the sky unlocks the possibility of constructing a rigid global stellar reference system.

The same sort of wide-angle measurements cannot be performed from the ground. This is mainly a result of atmospheric turbulence, which becomes worse away from the zenith, and makes wide-angle measurements even more error prone. It is compounded by gravitational instrument flexure, and other complexities.

